

Gender Equality
GE ACADEMY

D7.2 Dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement activities progress report version 1 (VIL)

December, 2019

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**Deliverable 7.2: Dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement activities
progress report version 1**

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1. Executive Summary

The GE Academy project aims at developing and implementing a high-quality capacity-building programme on gender equality in research, innovation and higher education. The capacity-building programme will be based on state-of-the-art knowledge and composed of a series of tailor-made training materials and different training formats (including: Physical Trainings, Summer Schools, Physical Interactive workshops, Webinars, Distributive Open Collaborative Courses (DOCCs), Train-the-Trainer sessions) and it will be executed in at least 15 countries. At the same time, a pan-European network of gender trainers, both female and male, will be established so as to trainers, practitioners and researchers will be trained, coached and upskilled for delivering gender training sessions tailored to the R&I and HE communities all over Europe and beyond.¹

In this respect, key for the achievement of the ambitious objectives of GE Academy is the implementation of the highly effective dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement strategy (D7.1) that ensures:

- The wider promotion and outreach of the project to critical stakeholders to speed up its wider use and impact to the economy and the society.
- The communication of the benefits and opportunities offered through our programmes and activities.
- The engagement and involvement of key stakeholders in the project's activities.
- The development and sustainability of the overall project and the pan-European network of gender trainers and other relevant stakeholders.
- The exploitation of the project results and the sustainability of the proposed activities and overall approach.

This report is based on the first version of D7.1 "Dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement strategy". The first version was developed during M3 and the final one will be submitted to the EC by the end of the project (M36).

This deliverable D7.2 provides an overview of the activities conducted during the first year of the project (M1-M12). It describes the progress and statistics of the communication activities (online and offline) including the project website, social media channels, newsletters, videos, press releases, third-party events and attempts to indicate any changes or improvements in relation to the initial strategy and plan. It is essential to mention that during this project period efforts were focused on the design and implementation of activities for the pilot testing of the first GE Academy training sessions under WP4 (webinars, workshops, in-person training sessions) as well as preparation for the roll-out phase (WP5).

¹ GE Academy Grant Agreement

2. Introduction

This report presents the updated dissemination and communication strategy of the project, focusing on making some particular dissemination channels and tools more effective to reach a wider audience for the roll-out of the GE Academy programme, to continue disseminating this programme to relevant target groups and stakeholders across Europe and beyond. This is also the progress report presenting the communication achievements of GE Academy (M1-M12).

In particular, GE Academy tools and activities include both online and offline, such as:

- A dedicated project website (<https://ge-academy.eu/>) allowing for fast and easy communication of the most relevant information and news to a broad audience and to the appropriate target groups looking for opportunities to receive gender training.
- Social media channels to communicate the activities and value of the project.
 - Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/GEAcademy.eu/>)
 - Twitter (https://twitter.com/GEAcademy_eu)
 - LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/18976416/>)
- Newsletters and press releases to inform relevant stakeholders about the key achievements of the GE Academy project and next activities planned.
- Participation in external events and organisation of dedicated sessions with the main purpose of getting potential stakeholders directly involved in the network but also for gathering feedback about the activities performed by the Consortium.
- Coordination with relevant projects towards joint dissemination efforts.
- Printed material
- Various other activities and tactics

The project communication and dissemination tools and activities are being reviewed and updated on a regular basis for assessing new and possible dissemination opportunities that emerge during the project implementation. The updated strategy was conceived after the second semester's internal review of the dissemination activities (M6) and was designed given the preparation of the first pilot implementation phase (M8). It was tailored to fit the project time plan.

2.1 Document structure

This introduction is followed by a presentation of the updated dissemination and communication strategy (section 3). The subsequent section 4 is dedicated to the reporting of the activities conducted during year 1 (M1-M12). In addition, section 5 provides the progress in numbers and the overall monitoring approach of the communication activities. Lastly, section 6 provides a few conclusions and next steps for the forthcoming period.

3. Updated Dissemination and Communication Strategy

This section provides a short overview of the projects dissemination and communication strategy as presented in D7.1 Dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement strategy together with some important updates that were decided among partners in order to make the overall dissemination activities more effective towards the promotion of the roll-out programme according to the suggestions made via D1.2 Guidelines for promoting capacity building on GE in research.

In M6 and M12 during the physical project meetings in Paris and Budapest, partners performed an internal assessment of their dissemination activities and they decided on a set of specific changes focusing on the following core elements of the communication and dissemination strategy:

- Communication and dissemination Tools and Channels: Particular emphasis should be given at the project website by improving the online content by the end of year 1 and in view of the initiation of the roll-out. In addition, extra efforts should be dedicated to social media and a stronger link with partner's social media and online accounts.
- Design of material: A set of needed material was requested from WP4 and WP5 contributors to facilitate the promotion of a common visual identity for the promotion of training sessions and their roll-out.
- Reporting and Evaluation: More systemic reporting and evaluation activities among partners.

Since October 2019 (M10), the project has realised its first set of training sessions in different places across Europe and online via webinars, and attention was given so that dissemination and communication components would be key parts of these sessions. In this context, the overall promotion of GE Academy was based on the promotion of each and every one of the capacity building activities. The reason for such course of actions was that during the first year, it was essential for GE Academy to reach out audience and relevant stakeholders through tangible outcomes and with an engaging fashion.

As a result, the different training sessions of GE Academy fuelled and fed back into the dissemination and communication objectives of the project. What is more, the actualisation of such events took carefully into account the guideline material sourced in D1.2 "Guidelines for promoting capacity-building on GE in research (CNRS)", in which a series of recommendations about the organisation of capacity building events was enlisted. Consequently, GE Academy held two webinars, two workshops and two in-person training sessions which were aligned with the aforementioned guidelines.

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First, the capacity building sessions addressed the need for careful consideration and selection of enablers and co-hosting organisations. That is, training sessions, particularly the real-life events, featured gender experts as facilitators and the organisation was jointly undertaken with research institutes based on European locations.

Second, these events took place after bearing in mind that apart from the addressed topic, there were specific needs in terms of location and audience. In other words, training sessions of GE Academy were organised so that particular necessities could be covered as well. Therefore, webinars were scheduled on commonly convenient hours in Central European Time, and real-life events were performed according to the participants needs (e.g. in-person training in Montpellier, France, was held in French).

Third, the actual format, likewise the above, was formed to be participant/attendee centric and to prompt an interactive delivery method. The training sessions focused on engaging the audience in active learning and having them produce their testimonies according to the information that was communicated to them.

Fourth, the customisation of the training sessions based on the audience traits was pivotal to secure that projected stakeholders who could bring institutional change in favour of gender equality would be the primary recipients of GE Academy's actions. What is more, the tailored content elaboration has also opted so that awareness could be raised for the scope of the project. Through the accurate and comprehensive communication of the training sessions' content, GE Academy secured an effective promotion overall.

Fifth, the dissemination and communication needs of the project overlap with its objective to form an extensive network of facilitators to hold capacity building events collaboratively. It was, then, purposeful to roll out its first series of training actions including varying topics and challenges. In this way, GE Academy worked towards disseminating its actions to stakeholders such as researchers in academic institutions and officers of the business sector. At the same time, it addressed its main objective of fostering awareness to such change-factors about gender equality.

Sixth, the project has adopted a specific procedure of monitoring and evaluation of such events. This procedure is projected to enhance the organisation of future training sessions as it is set to provide the consortium with insights about the efficiency of the actions taken. Feedback from participants was collected after the events; its careful examination among project partners has been a valuable process so far, hence it is a critical component of events and the dissemination evaluation as well.

Last, the completed events have also been discussed in GE Academy's website at the dedicated section of the news. What is more, a repository section has been created on the project's website to operate as a digital library and resource access point, where the training sessions' material is going to be progressively available.

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3.1 Project website

Among the tools that are being implemented to disseminate GE Academy, it was agreed that emphasis should be given at improving the project's website and promotion activities in social media. Moreover, due to the release of the first webinars, a YouTube channel was created to support their dissemination.

After the internal communication and dissemination assessment, partners were asked to review the project website and provide their suggestions for improvements. During the 3rd partners' meeting in Budapest in M12, the various suggestions were presented, and partners agreed to implement the following changes:

- Change the menu header in solid white so the letters are more visible.
- Create individual pages about the different training sessions when registration/application period is open.
- Add a new menu item "Resources", where the material of training sessions will become easily accessible.
- Update the project calendar.
- Update the different pages header with images.
- Update several pages with more information.

As a result, the website has a fresher look and it is able to provide with the correct information in a few clicks. Below, we present a few details about its new pages that are not included in D7.1.

Figure 1. Website – Training offer preview

Training offer (<https://ge-academy.eu/gender-trainings>): This section is mainly dedicated providing information about what gender trainings are, who they are for, how you can register/apply etc. This page includes direct links to other pages based on the format. It acts as a key entry point of information and it is highlighted in the website.

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Calendar (<https://ge-academy.eu/calendar>): This section is dedicated to provide information about training opportunities, including the links to enrol, the specific dates, etc. At this point, it is in a starting stage and it will be developed by the beginning of January 2020 to reflect the roll-out programme.

Project resources (<https://ge-academy.eu/resources/>) containing completed webinars, useful material, media kit, deliverables, other project resources made available to public.

3.2 Social media and online channels

Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn

Social media channels are being used as described in D7.1 with a few examples below. Messages are tailored to the characters and length permitted by each channel, while images are being used and relevant partners and accounts are being tagged to reshare the posts.

Figure 2. Implementation of a social media campaign – Examples

To enhance any promotional efforts, partners received the following tips during the 2nd partners meeting in Paris (June 2019, M6):

Use your organizational or/and personal accounts to increase visibility of the project and its account by:

- Posting regularly project news and activities and activate your network (Proposed frequency: 1-2 times/week)
- Use live blogging especially on Twitter to post pictures of events or project activities and write motivational quotes, interesting facts, etc.
- When posting, make sure to tag the project accounts and tag relevant Consortium partners to ensure a bigger outreach and attention.

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- Use hashtags such as #GEAcademy, #genderequality, #h2020, it is a simple and effective SEO practice to increase project's visibility on social networks.
- Tag the European Commission or relevant DGs with organizational accounts.

Except for communication through partners accounts, cross-posting is recommended to host institutions and speakers of the training sessions to ensure a wide spread of the word about the sessions. VIL is in contact with them to advise and learn the different opportunities for the most effective promotion. In addition, the following image is being sent to host organisations, participants and speakers to ensure they have in mind to post about the sessions.

GE ACADEMY SOCIAL MEDIA: 3 KEY THINGS

We are counting on you to interact on social media

- https://twitter.com/GEAcademy_eu - follow us on Twitter & use the tags **@GEAcademy_eu** in your posts, use our hashtag **#GEAcademy**
- Like us on Facebook (**@GEAcademy.eu**) and LinkedIn (**GE Academy**) and feel free to tag us on your text and picture posts
- Feel free to promote further trainings in your networks and help us get new high-level registrants.

Thank you for helping us share the knowledge, and spread the GE Academy effect!

On another note: we will be very glad to share your content and retweet your posts.

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**Gender Equality
GE ACADEMY**

Figure 3. Social media | 3 Key things

YouTube channel

A YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCGLibmdaDB8TPMRIFufDiNQ>) was created to cover the need of publishing the project videos in a platform other than the Facebook Page. So far, two (2) videos have been published, while a few of them have been promoted along with the channel itself. The main aim of the channel developed is to showcase the webinars performed during the first project period and therefore to attract high quality participants for our next set of activities. In addition, the YouTube channel will act as the space where all webinars will be published to ensure their wide dissemination, so more increased traffic and activity is expected the following months as the roll-out phase includes more topics and sessions.

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Figure 4. YouTube Channel

3.3 Material developed

The development of the GE Academy branding was a key priority from the beginning of the project in order to create a single visual identity and make it easily identifiable by the target audiences. All project material developed includes in a prominent position the EU Funding visibility.

The branding pack for the roll-out programme prepared by VIL and it is used by all project members and relevant actors and includes:

- Project leaflet
- Social media images - promotional templates
- Agenda template for the training sessions
- Template for trainer's presentation
- Script template
- Handout template
- Certificate of attendance

Most of the abovementioned material is being used by the host institutions of different training sessions to run local promotion and they are tailored to each individual purpose, audience and session according to the needs indicated by the host organisation in cooperation with VIL, relevant partners and the careful evaluation from YW.

Social media images - promotional templates

Promotion via social media and online channels is highly important due to the nature of the registration form which is offered online. These templates have been developed to facilitate the promotion of the sessions to a wider audience and boost the accompanying messages on different

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online platforms by offering a quick set of important information including the topic of the session, the format, the date, the location and the message that registration is open. In addition, for the in-person training and workshop emphasis is also given to the promotion of the host organisation. In the images below, you can see a few examples of those images.

Figure 5. Social media promotional messages

These images are offered to partners, the host organisations and any promotion partners for use. Since, they are in high quality, they can also act as a printed flyer.

Agenda template for the training sessions

Another important template for the promotion of the training sessions is the one containing the agenda and the overview of the training, thus delivering information about the actual content of the session. The agenda includes the learning objectives, the name of the facilitator resp. trainer, other details, the agenda and in the case of the webinars, it also includes a short bio of the speakers and details on how to connect and attend the webinar.

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Title of the training session
Location/date (e.g. Thessaloniki, 12 December 2019)

Trainer(s): Name/Surname (e.g. Maxime Forest | Lucy Ferguson)

Learning objectives:

- Provide an overview of the main imbalances and bias with regard to HR management in research and the academia (vertical and horizontal segregation, gender pay gap, international mobility)
- 3
- 4
- Etc.

Provisional agenda

Time	Topic
09.00 – 09.30	Welcome & Intro

Registration link:
<https://ge-academy.eu/in-person-training/>

Key-note speakers

Maria Sanguilano
Maria Sanguilano, PhD in Cognitive and Learning Studies, senior gender expert and researcher, has 20 years' experience in EU funded projects and programmes on gender equality. Her research and work is located at the intersections between social and technological innovation to make innovation policies and processes more sustainable and inclusive through diversity sensitive co-design and participatory design methods. Among her most recent endeavours, Maria was in charge of supporting the recently concluded H2020 EQUAL-151 partners in achieving institutional change for gender equality and is currently leading the Smart Venice team in the GE Academy consortium and other projects.

Paula Wennberg
Paula Wennberg, Centre for Distance-spanning Technology, Luleå University of Technology, Sweden. Paula Wennberg is Founder and Manager of Gender Contact Point, a collaboration and resource platform based at Luleå University of Technology, Sweden. She has 20 years' experience of regional, national and European collaborative projects and has developed a great number of gender equality and diversity tools and methods promoting inclusive innovation and research. She is currently the coordinator of the Gender Smart Arena project with partners from ICT companies and municipalities. The project supports strategic business activities as well as gender mainstreaming processes of academia, industry and surrounding society.

Anne Laure Humbert
Anne Laure Humbert, PhD, is a Reader in Gender and Diversity and Director of the Centre for Diversity Policy Research and Practice at Oxford Brookes University. Anne has worked extensively on developing methodologies and indicators for measuring gender equality in multiple settings. Some of the recent and current projects include looking at the impact of gender and diversity in STEM research teams (GEDII), implementing gender equality plans in universities across Europe (GEARING-Roles), gender in spinouts company in the UK. Some recent publications include: "A rights-based approach to board quotas and how hard sanctions work for gender equality", European Journal of Women, and "The perils of gender beliefs for men leaders as change agents for gender equality" European Management Review 2018.

Simonetta Manfredi
Simonetta Manfredi is Professor of Equality and Diversity Management, and Associate Dean for Research and Knowledge Exchange in the Business School at Oxford Brookes University in the UK. She is the founding director of the Oxford Brookes Centre for Diversity Policy and Practice, that she established in 2004 and is based in the Business School. Her research interests and expertise are primarily focused on gender and leadership, age discrimination and retirement policies, work-life balance, and applied diversity policy research in the Higher Education sector. She is currently leading a two-years project funded by the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council to increase the representation of women researchers in STEM as founders and co-founders of university spinout companies. Simonetta is regularly invited to speak at academic and practitioner conferences and her work has been featured by the press and media. She is co-author of Managing Equality and Diversity, published by Oxford University Press, which received the Chartered Management Institute Management Book of the Year Award in 2013 (under the management and leadership category).

Figure 6. Training session – Agenda template

Template for trainer's presentation

During the presentations of webinars or any other format of training session, it is essential to ensure the visibility of the GE Academy branding identity and highlight that those sessions are offered for free under the GE Academy project. For this reason, a PowerPoint template tailored to the needs of facilitators, trainers and speakers has been developed and it is offered by the respective task leaders.

1. Title slide with GE Academy logo and presentation title.

2. Blank slide with GE Academy logo and funding notice.

3. Slide with GE Academy logo, main title, and a decorative line of dots.

4. Blank slide with GE Academy logo and funding notice.

5. Slide with GE Academy logo and the text "Time for a Brake!".

6. Slide with GE Academy logo, a quote icon, and the text "ADD TEXT/QUOTE".

Figure 7. Template for trainer's presentation

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Script template

Scripts for the training sessions are being prepared by YW and the WP4 contributors and they are communicated to external experts for review under WP2. For this reason, a script template has been developed to ensure an aligned visual identity of the documents shared with external experts.

Figure 8. Script template

Handout template

A handout template has also been developed. This template is being used by the facilitators resp. trainers and those developing the content of each training session. Those handouts are being printed by the host organisations and they are distributed to the participants of each session.

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Figure 9. Handout template

Certificate of attendance

A certificate of attendance is given to those attending any physical training sessions of the project. Its format is below. The content of the certificate has not been validated by WP4 and WP5 contributors and it will be done by M13.

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Figure 10. Certificate of attendance template

Project leaflet

Figure 11. Project leaflet – Outline

A project leaflet has been designed according to the briefing provided by partners. After a selection process, partners decided on the following outline.

The content of the leaflet is to be validated and comments will be provided on M13. Thus, the leaflet will be ready for printing by the end of M13 and it can act as another material for distribution of information about the GE Academy project.

3.4 Other communication tactics

Spreading the word | Acting as local ambassadors

The regional networks of each partner are very valuable to this cause. Thus, partners should give emphasis on engaging with the community and the stakeholders of their region. The goal of GE Academy is to extend training sessions in a pan-European level, so that the partners will operate as local ambassadors to:

- Attract more significant volumes of audience and amplify the reach of the organised training activities.
- Cluster with local projects and /or initiatives that are active on the issue of Gender Equality, to allocate more potential contributors, that is, hosts for GE Academy's activities or potential replicators.
- Foster a greater awareness of the project, and consequently its objectives, in local communities.

4. Reporting on Communication and Dissemination activities (M1-M12)

4.1 Project website

The project website is used as one of the main communication and dissemination tools of the project. During the first year of the project, we used the project's website to:

- Provide information about the project and help stakeholders understand why they might want to get involved and how they can participate in the project's activities and use its results.
- Provide information as a central point for the available training sessions.
- Make available the available project outputs.
- Publish the project news.
- Publicise the project dissemination material, newsletters and public deliverables.

Website performance

In order to assess how well the website is reaching stakeholders and acting as a source of information, we use standard web traffic analysis tool (Google Analytics) to track the number of visitors and similar metrics over the life of the project.

Figure 12. Google Analytics – Audience overview lifetime

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In the above figure, the results from the first reporting period are presented with an audience overview. The terms used in this figure as well as the results are described here:

- 4,169 Sessions. A session is the period time a user is actively engaged with your website, app, etc. All usage data (Screen Views, Events, Ecommerce, etc.) is associated with a session.
- 2,713 Users. Users have initiated at least one session during the date range.
- 14,027 Page Views. Pageviews include the total number of pages viewed. Repeated views of a single page are counted.

The figure shows that increased traffic performed during the months September 2019 to November 2019 when the different training sessions were available for registration.

Figure 13. Google Analytics - Landing pages per pageviews

Overall, the promotion and communication of the project and its activities was successful, especially since the main aim was to showcase and attract audience for its training sessions, which were the most popular URLs as shown in the figure above.

4.2 Social media and online channels

Social media channels are an integral part of our communication and dissemination strategy as they provide the chance to get connected and reach regions and stakeholders all over the world. The aim of this section is to present the basic elements of the social media strategy and the results of the first reporting period (M1-M12) per social media channel.

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Facebook

Figure 14. GE Academy – Facebook Page

GE Academy has a Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/GEAcademy.eu/>) which currently counts 321 followers. According to the figure below, the audience of the page is coming mainly from the project partners countries (Greece, Italy, Germany, Hungary, Czech Republic, Belgium, Norway, etc.) and 55% of the followers are women, while men represent the 43%.

Figure 15. Facebook page – Audience breakdown

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Twitter

GE Academy has a Twitter account (https://twitter.com/GEAcademy_eu) which currently counts 360 followers.

Figure 16. GE Academy – Twitter account

According to its analytics, Twitter account offers the biggest visibility in comparison with the other project channels. The number of followers, impressions, reshares and clicks on the different tweet links indicates a good number of engagement, which is visible in the following figures. Specifically, during October and November 2019 (M10-M11), numbers are high due to the promotion of the first pilot training sessions of GE Academy.

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Figure 17. Analytics of October and November 2019

While, during a 90 days period, the account earned 44.6K impressions with over 290 link clicks.

Figure 18. 90 days overview – Twitter analytics

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LinkedIn

GE Academy has a LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/18976416/>) to get in touch with the professional network. According to the LinkedIn analytics, GE Academy's account is followed by researchers, people in higher education, etc. which are among the target audiences of GE Academy's training sessions.

YouTube Analytics

GE Academy's YouTube channel is newly developed and only two videos of the two recent webinars have been posted. Due to its recent launch, analytics can offer limited results, thus more results will be provided in the next interim report (D7.3).

4.3 External events and meetings

[EQUAL-IST Final conference: Gender Equality Policies in Research Institutions: Promoting transformative and sustainable changes](#)

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Date: 22 May 2019

Location: Brussels, Belgium

Description: This was the final Conference on Gender Equality Policies in Research Institutions: Promoting transformative and sustainable changes, and it was conducted on 22nd May in Brussels. The aim was to introduce the H2020 EQUAL-IST project results and tools, to the scientific and policy community across Europe that built along the last three years of implementation. The major scope was to discuss opportunities to innovate at teaching, students' services, HR management and Institutional communication via gender equality.

Lut Mergaert of Yellow Window took part in the event to present GE Academy to the Conference audience comprised majorly by relevant stakeholders. The session was facilitated by Maria Sanguiliano (SV) and the event was organized by VIL.

Video recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PimbF7GIHFA&feature=emb_title

[Austrian Workshop: "Genderkompetenz-Trainings für EvaluatorenInnen"](#)

Date: 23 May 2019

Location: Vienna, Austria

Description: The workshop was an event organised by the Working Group Gender Mainstreaming of DeGEval – Evaluation Society, a co-operation of persons and institutions that are active in the field of evaluation. (Arbeitskreis Gender Mainstreaming der DeGEval – Gesellschaft für Evaluation e.V.). The aim of the workshop was to share experiences when designing and implementing

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gender competence trainings for individuals assigned with evaluation tasks in their relevant sector.

Project partner B-NK (Bente Knoll) took part in the workshop to deliver an overview presentation of GE Academy's scope on providing capacity building training about gender equality plans implementation in Research and Innovation as well as in the Higher Education fields.

Italian Workshop: "Innovare le organizzazioni di ricerca attraverso l'uguaglianza di genere e Laboratorio di co-progettazione"

Date: 11 June 2019

Location: Venice, Italy

The workshop, which is translated as 'Innovating research organizations through gender equality' was organized by the regional project "Veneto in Azione", and it was the third part of an action series based on Gender Equality promotion, the main scope of the aforementioned project.

Maria Sangiuliano of Smart Venice presented and promoted the GE Academy project and invited the participants to join the forthcoming trainings.

Research and Innovation Excellence through gender equality: New pathways and challenges

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Date: 23 – 24 October 2019

Location: Helsinki, Finland

Description: This conference was held to put together a paper outlining what Europe needed to do to ensure gender equality in research and innovation in the future. The two-day event culminated in publishing a co-created Helsinki Call for Action. Speakers and participants represented the research community, research funding institutions, top policymakers, innovation actors, the digital and tech industry, and NGOs. Former president and the first female head of state of Finland, Tarja Halonen, was the keynote speaker.

Yellow Window took part in the event to represent GE Academy and provided input for the Conference's main output: the Helsinki Call for Action. (The Helsinki Call for Action can also be downloaded in PDF [here](#))

[Smart City Expo World Congress](#)

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Date: 19 – 21 November 2019

Location: Barcelona, Spain

Description: Smart City Expo World Congress is an annual conference aimed to empower cities and collectivize urban innovation across the globe. Through promoting social innovation, establishing partnerships and identifying business opportunities, the event is dedicated to creating a better future for cities and their citizens worldwide. It comprised a three-day program with +400 international experts coming together to share insights and learn best practices for a more sustainable urban world. In this context a keynote featured the thematic of INCLUSIVE & SHARING CITIES, during which one of the debated topics referred on 'Bridging the Gap / Ensuring Digital, Social and Gender Inclusion'

GE Academy partners from UPM took part on this event to network with relevant stakeholders, present the project's objectives and communicate its projected Summer School Action. This is the [list of featured speakers](#) where Ines Sánchez de Madariaga is highlighted.

4th Industrial Revolution and Ethics

Date: 21 – 22 November 2019

Location: Madrid

Description: The Congress was organised by European Women Lawyers Association (EWLA) as a framework for reflection with policy makers and business leaders to create an inclusive future and humanize technologies. to tackle these challenges with a triangle integration approach: education, business, innovation. The event's scope argued that there is a need for innovative and

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human centred actions, to mitigate current and forthcoming challenges and to foster our democracies and promote the creation of a world transition to a greener, healthier and more sustainable future.

GE Academy Partners from UPM took part on this event to network with relevant stakeholders, present the project's objectives and communicate its projected Summer Schools.

[French Networking Event: Info day on H2020 Swafs projects: Journée nationale & Science avec et pour la Société - Horizon 2020 à Horizon Europe](#)

Date: 28 November 2019

Location, Paris, France

Description: The National Science Contact Point with and for the Horizon2020 Society organized the annual national day dedicated to the SwafS program on November 28, 2019 in the premises of the Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation. The event consisted on two parts. During the morning part, the proceedings aimed to inform about the last wave of calls for projects whose opening is fixed for December 10. Representatives of funded projects from previous years also shared their experience of European projects. The afternoon part was devoted to the place of science-society themes within Horizon Europe, the future framework program for research and innovation.

GE Academy partners from CNRS participated to the networking event in order to deliver a presentation of the project.

In addition, VIL (Coordinator) and YW (Scientific Coordinator) attended multiple meetings with relevant stakeholders in their home countries and beyond. Worth mentioning are the following: VIL is in touch with the European Institute of Gender Equality (EIGE). A few representatives met with the Deputy Coordinator in the premises of EIGE on June 2019. Moreover, YW is in continuous liaison with the Policy Officers of the Gender Equality and Diversity division of the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation of the EC to inform them about the project progress and our next steps. Lastly, partners will continue their efforts towards presenting the project to their network and spreading the word about GE Academy and its activities throughout Europe.

4.4 Newsletter and Press Releases

At the moment, one (1) newsletter has been developed and shared with the GE Academy community, while the mailing list has over 300 subscribers. We use MailChimp as the platform to develop our newsletters and the visual results for the first campaign are shown below. This newsletter included information about i) general information about the project, ii) announcement of the pilot training sessions with registration links, iii) a call for host organisations, and iv) presentation of the partnership. In addition, links to the website and different social media channels were visible. The results of the campaign were quite successful given a 49.1% of opening rate and the click-through rate of 26.5% with the most popular links being the ones of the training sessions.

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On the occasion of the promotion of the training sessions, a press release was produced and disseminated through various channels from all partners. This is a generic one that was sent centrally. More press releases were developed for the needs of the host institutions to run a local promotion for the in-person training sessions and the workshops attracting participants nationwide. More press releases will be available from M13 onwards starting with the announcement of the application form to become a gender trainer for GE Academy.

Figure 19. Welcome newsletter and Press Release

Both newsletters and press releases are published on the project website: <https://ge-academy.eu/press-kit/>

4.5 Synergies with other projects and initiatives

GE Academy is a proud member of Eurogender (<https://eurogender.eige.europa.eu/users/gender-equality-academy>) (powered by the European Institute of Gender Equality (EIGE), an online consultation and cooperation platform). GE Academy uploads its new and events via the platform to notify the relevant community.

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Figure 20. GE Academy announcement of its webinar on Eurogender

GE Academy publishes its news about upcoming training sessions on Eurogender as relevant actors are being informed via notifications and emails.

GE Academy organised its second workshop “Dealing with resistances” in Barcelona, Spain in cooperation with the ACT project.

GE Academy is in continuous liaison with the communication team of Gearing Roles for cross-promoting content for both projects. In addition, GE Academy is featured on the Gearing Roles website (<https://gearingroles.eu/sister-projects/>), while YW team attended its conference. Lastly, Gearing Roles partners Anne Laure Humbert and Simonetta Manfredi from the Oxford Brookes University participated in the 2nd webinar of GE Academy presenting the following topic: "Women and Innovation: the case of University spinout companies".

GE Academy partners attended its final conference and presented the project. In addition, GE Academy was featured on its newsletters.

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GE Academy was featured in one of the project's newsletters with an interview from Lut Mergaert and Vasiliki Madesi (<https://ge-academy.eu/ge-uploads/2019/09/4th-GEECCO-Newsletter.pdf>), while Amaia Lusa Garcia, UPC, professor of Industrial Engineering presented the topic: "Gender Equality at Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya" during the 1st webinar of GE Academy.

GENDER-SMART representatives participated in the in-person training "How to avoid gender bias in recruitment and promotion?".

Supera project representatives participated in the in-person training "How to avoid gender bias in recruitment and promotion?".

More activities and opportunities for collaboration will take place during the second year of the project. GE Academy is already in discussion with partners from different projects for hosting the upcoming training sessions and participating in the webinars.

4.6 Promotion through partners' networks

Partners use their own social media accounts to disseminate the project and its activities. The reason is that partners have already thousands of followers in social media and trust is already established between them and their followers. Partners are tagged in project announcements and posts and their reshares help the project to achieve a bigger visibility. A few examples can be found below:

Figure 21. Smart Venice sample posts about GE Academy

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Figure 22. K-RCN sample posts about GE Academy

In addition, partners upload information about the project on their website pages and their newsletters.

Figure 23. GE Academy as seen on the website of CNRS and the newsletter of ISAS

5. Monitoring and evaluation

As the actions of GE Academy are increasing and the reach of the project is steadily growing, it is necessary to keep track of the communication and dissemination activities of partners in a more accurate form. The project adopted a standardized reporting procedure, which will be valuable in order to assess the efficiency of the consortium in terms of promoting GE Academy's actions and achieving the projected impact. To allow an adequate monitoring of the communication and dissemination activities and understand the impact generated by these activities, partners are requested to report their relevant actions carried out using a specific reporting template (see Annex I). In addition, specific performance indicators have been developed from the beginning of the project in order to allow comparisons between the planned and actual activities as well as their effectiveness to reach their goals.

This deliverable provides an overview of the communication and dissemination activities during year 1, while this section presents the relevant key performance indicators and their progress.

5.1 Key Performance Indicators

The table below provides a summary of the project online and offline performance, which is considered sufficient taking into account the preparation phase during year 1 as well as the use of the partners' online and offline channels as key dissemination tools. These numbers are expected to significantly increase during the second project year particularly due to the initiation of the roll-out phase of the GE Academy's programme, thus reaching and exceeding the target values of the project.

Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Target value (M36)	Current status (M12)
Social Media		
No. of Twitter followers	600	360
No. of likes on Facebook	400	312
No. of Project videos	5	2
No. of views on YouTube	200 per video	100 views in total YouTube is a newly launched channel which is expected to be used during the second year of the project
Website		
No. of accesses per year	2,000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4,169 Sessions • 2,713 Users

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No. of downloads of deliverables	300	n/a during this period Public deliverables will become available after EC's approval
No. of individuals / organisations signed up to receive email updates on project progress	150 by M24 300 by M36	300 subscribers
Peer reviewed scientific papers, conference publications & policy briefs		
No. of manuscripts accepted for publication	2	n/a This task starts at a later stage
No. of policy briefs / white papers	2	n/a This task starts at a later stage
Events, conferences (Public awareness and sharing of experience with external experts in the field)		
Participation in conferences and workshops	10	7
Distribution of leaflets in events	at least 500	n/a Leaflet will be available from M13

6. Conclusion

This is the first reporting deliverable and it provides an insight of the project's dissemination and communication strategy and reports the progress achieved so far towards engaging its target groups. The deliverable covers the period between M1 to M12 flagged by the reassess of the strategy towards the promotion of the training sessions and the roll-out programme. This phase enabled the project partners to intensify the dissemination activities through the promotion of the project pilot sessions.

Overall, the results of this period (M1-M12) are satisfactory since all the goals and targets were achieved:

- More than 360 followers on Twitter while the overall project goal (M36) is 600 followers.
- More than 312 likes and follows on Facebook, while the overall project goal is 400 likes.
- The number of subscribers on the project newsletter has been achieved from this first year, while this number will be increased the following years.
- Participation and promotion of GE Academy in more than 7 relevant events and conferences.
- More than 4,169 session on the project website with 2,713 users were achieved.
- The target number of registrations and participants to the pilot sessions was achieved.

Overall, all the expected results for this period have been reached. The efforts managed to achieve more than expected and created a strong network of GE Academy followers which is still expanding. The results of this period give us the confidence to engage with more people and relevant groups and achieve even greater results for the following critical year of the roll-out programme.

7. Annex

Annex I: Communication and Dissemination Reporting

The form is available via this link: <https://forms.gle/E3Esgk7nFa5Eaj9> It is used as an easy to use tool to report any communication and dissemination activities. Partners are able to choose their organisation, the type of the activity (the list is based on the ECAS portal) and upload any relevant attachments.

